

Kinetics and Mechanism of Bromination of Phenol and Substituted Phenols by *N*-Bromobenzamide in Aquo-acetic Acid Medium

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Kinetics of bromination of phenol and substituted phenols by *N*-bromobenzamide have been studied in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) medium. The rates of bromination show first order kinetics in [NBB], fractional order in [phenols] and zero order in [H⁺]. The rate slightly decreases with the addition of the reduced product of the oxidant, while the increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent decreases the rate. A Michaelis-Menten type mechanism is suggested to account for the results. The coefficients of the rate-limiting steps and the corresponding activation parameters have been computed. The rate constants recalculated from the rate laws agree reasonably well with the experimental constants, checking the consistency of the suggested mechanism. The validity of the Hammett equation has also been tested.

The chemistry of phenols is of interest as they form an important class of aromatic compounds. As part of our mechanistic studies with biologically and industrially interesting compounds¹, we report herein the kinetics of bromination of phenols and substituted phenols by *N*-bromobenzamide in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid and benzamide.

Results and Discussion

The reactions show first order in [NBB] in all the cases (Table 1). The rates increased with increasing [phenols] with fractional order dependences

(Tables 1 and 2). The plots of either k_{obs} vs. [phenols] or the double reciprocal plots were linear (Figs. 1 and 2). The rates were unaffected by the variation in [HClO₄], but decreased with increase in added [benzamide] (BA), with an inverse fractional order dependence (Table 2). Variation in ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rates of bromination. The rates increased with increase in [mercuric acetate] and [sodium acetate]. A decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing acetic acid composition of the solvent decreased the rate in all the cases. The plots of log k_{obs} vs % AcOH or $1/D$ were linear with negative slopes.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE BROMINATION OF PHENOL AND SUBSTITUTED-PHENOLS BY *N*-BROMOBENZAMIDE (NBB) IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) ($I=0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) AT 293 K (313 K FOR *p*-NO₂ AND *m*-NO₂ PHENOLS)

$10^3[\text{NBB}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[\text{Phenol}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	Phenol		$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)							
			in absence of NaOAc	in presence of NaOAc	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	<i>o</i> -COOH
Effect of varying [NBB] ₀												
0.50	1.0	1.0	11.7	13.5	8.1	11.8	10.0	8.3	10.9	17.2	13.1	8.9
1.0	1.0	1.0	11.6	13.7	7.7	11.7	10.1	8.4	10.9	17.4	13.2	8.8
2.0	1.0	1.0	11.1	12.7	7.8	11.7	10.0	8.7	11.2	17.3	13.2	8.8
4.0	1.0	1.0	11.7	10.2	8.3	11.7	10.0	8.6	10.8	17.4	13.2	8.8
Effect of varying [Phenol] ₀												
1.0	0.50	1.0	—	11.3	5.7	9.2	8.7	5.0	7.2	14.8	11.1	7.6
1.0	0.75	1.0	10.7	13.3	6.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.0	1.0	11.6	13.7	7.7	11.7	10.1	8.4	10.9	17.4	13.2	8.8
1.0	2.0	1.0	15.3	14.8	8.7	—	11.4	13.9	19.9	19.6	14.8	10.2
1.0	3.0	1.0	17.3	15.2	—	15.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	4.0	1.0	—	15.5	10.4	—	12.1	23.4	33.1	24.5	17.7	11.5
1.0	5.0	1.0	21.3	15.8	—	16.7	12.5	27.6	41.7	26.3	19.5	—
1.0	6.0	1.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	12.0
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]												
1.0	1.0	0.20	11.1	13.5	7.6	—	10.1	8.5	11.3	17.0	13.3	—
1.0	1.0	0.50	10.9	13.8	7.7	11.0	10.2	8.4	10.9	17.2	13.1	8.5
1.0	1.0	1.0	11.6	13.7	7.7	11.7	10.1	8.4	10.8	17.4	13.2	8.8
1.0	1.0	2.0	11.8	13.2	7.8	—	10.7	8.1	10.9	17.3	13.1	—
1.0	1.0	5.0	12.3	13.0	8.1	12.2	11.4	8.4	10.4	17.4	13.4	9.6
1.0	1.0	10.0	12.9	13.1	8.5	13.5	11.8	8.8	10.8	—	13.2	11.5

$10[\text{BA}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 2—KINETIC AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE BROMINATION OF PHENOL AND SUBSTITUTED-PHENOLS BY *N*-BROMOBENZAMIDE (NBB) IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v)

Orders (<i>n</i>) observed in	Phenol in		<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>o</i> -COOH	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃
	in absence of NaOAc	in presence of NaOAc								
[NBB]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
[Phenols]	0.40	0.20	0.25	0.28	0.12	0.78	0.74	0.20	0.28	0.20
[BA]	-0.16	-0.17	-0.40	-0.14	-0.23	-0.19	-0.10	-0.20	-0.09	-0.12
[Hg(OAc) ₂]	0.11	0.37	0.25	0.06	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.20
[CH ₃ COO ⁻]	—	0.65	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Activation parameters :	Computed from <i>k₂</i> values					Computed from <i>k₁</i> values				
log <i>A</i>	8.71	8.28	8.80	4.44	8.18	9.95	12.96	9.30	10.49	10.93
<i>E_a</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)	63.6	62.0	65.6	40.3	62.1	74.5	91.5	68.4	67.4	70.7
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	59.0	60.2	60.0	37.4	59.7	72.9	88.7	58.0	53.1	52.1
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-93.9	-92.6	-95.6	-169.7	-96.4	-59.7	-15.4	-102.5	-92.8	-113.0
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	86.5	87.4	88.0	87.1	87.9	91.6	90.6	88.0	80.2	85.2

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[Phenols]$; $10^3[NBB]_0=10$ [BA]= $10^3[HClO_4]=200[Hg(OAc)_2]=1.0$ mol dm⁻³, solvent: aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm⁻³; temp.=293 K (313 K with *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂). (ii) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs [BA]; $10^3[NBB]_0=10^3$ [Phenol]₀= $10^3[HClO_4]=200[Hg(OAc)_2]=1.0$ mol dm⁻³; solvent: aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm⁻³; temp.=293 K (313 K with *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂). (a) Phenol in absence of NaOAc and (b) phenol in presence of NaOAc.

Fig. 2. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs [Phenol]; $10^3[NBB]_0=10$ [BA]= $10^3[HClO_4]=200[Hg(OAc)_2]=1.0$ mol dm⁻³. (ii) Plots of $1/(k-k_1[S])$ vs [BA]; $10^3[NBB]_0=10^3$ [Phenol]₀= $10^3[HClO_4]=1.0$ mol dm⁻³. Solvent: aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm⁻³, temp.=293 K.

Mechanisms of brominations: The kinetics of the reactions may be explained by a Michaelis-

Menten type mechanism (Scheme 1). The products were the respective brominated phenols.

The related rate laws are

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{NBB}]_0 [\text{S}]}{[\text{BA}] + K_1 [\text{S}]} \quad (1)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{S}]}{[\text{BA}] + K_1 [\text{S}]} \quad (2)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{BA}]}{K_1 k_2} \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (3)$$

The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{BA}]$ (Fig. 1) were reasonably linear for bromination of most of the phenols. The constants K_1 and k_2 calculated from the former plot were used to recalculate the rate constants as $[\text{BA}]$ was varied and vice versa. A reasonably good agreement between the recalculated values and the experimental constants (Table 4) support the suggested mechanism.

Further, [phenols] were varied at different temperatures and the constants k_2 and K_1 at each temperature and the corresponding activation parameters were computed (Table 2).

p-Methyl- and *m*-methylphenols were the exceptions to the Michaelis-Menten type mechanism. Here direct plots gave better correlations than reciprocal plots (Fig. 2). The results observed under these conditions may be explained by a two-pathway mechanism (Scheme 2).

Path 1 :

Path 2 :

The related rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBB}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{NBB}] [\text{S}] + \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2 [\text{NBB}]_0}{K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + [\text{BA}]} \quad (4)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 [\text{S}] + \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2}{K_3 + [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + [\text{BA}]} \quad (5)$$

The rate law (6) may be rearranged as

$$k_{\text{obs}} - k_1 [\text{S}] = \frac{K'_2 k_3}{K'_3 + [\text{BA}]} \quad (6)$$

where, $K'_3 = K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $k'_3 = k_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}} - k_1 [\text{S}]} = \frac{[\text{BA}]}{K'_3 k'_3} + \frac{1}{k'_3} \quad (7)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{S}]$ and $1/(k_{\text{obs}} - k_1 [\text{S}])$ vs $[\text{BA}]$ were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Fig. 2) in accordance with the rate laws (5) and (7). The constants K'_3 and k'_3 calculated from the intercepts and slopes of the latter plots were used to recalculate the rate constants from the rate law (5) as $[\text{S}]$ were varied. Reasonable agreement between the recalculated values and the experimental constants supports the two-pathway mechanism in the cases.

A detailed mechanism of bromination is shown in Scheme 3.

The formation of dienone intermediate is also a frequently observed phenomenon².

Applicability of Hammett equation has also been tested. Equation (8) is found to be valid with the phenols for which σ values are available (Fig. 3).

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -2.16 - 1.3 \sigma \quad (8)$$

The negative value for the reaction constant and

Fig. 3. Plots of (i) $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs σ and (ii) ΔH^{\ddagger} vs ΔS^{\ddagger} .

the kinetic data indicate that electron-releasing substituents on the benzene ring of phenol accelerate the rate of bromination whereas electron-withdrawing groups retard it.

TABLE 3—COEFFICIENTS OF RATE-CONTROLLING STEPS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR THE BROMINATION OF PHENOLS BY *N*-BROMOBENZAMIDE (NBB) IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v)

[Phenol]	$10^3 k_2^a$ at			
	288 K	293 K	298 K	303 K
Phenol (in presence of NaOAc)	1.0	1.7	2.4	—
Phenol (in absence of NaOAc)	1.5	2.3	3.5	5.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.85	1.3	1.9	2.9
<i>o</i> -Cl	0.84	1.3	1.9	2.9
<i>m</i> -Cl	0.68	1.3	1.8	—
	293 K	303 K	313 K	318 K
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.52	1.3	3.3	5.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.55	1.7	5.0	10.0
	$10^3 k_1^b$			
	288 K	293 K	298 K	
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	17.3	30.0	45.5	
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	12.9	21.4	32.9	

^aCalculated from eqn. (3). ^bCalculated from eqn. (7).

Relatively large negative entropy of activation and high positive free energy of activation may suggest the role of bond-breaking in attaining the activated state. Plot of ΔH^{\ddagger} vs ΔS^{\ddagger} was also

linear (Fig. 3) with an isokinetic temperature of 308 K, which lies in the temperature range of 283—318 K employed in the present investigations.

The observed decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Table 2) is in conformity with Amis-Jaffe equation for dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interactions³.

Experimental

N-Bromobenzamide (NBB) was prepared by the action of sodium hypobromite on benzamide⁴. Purity of the oxidant was checked by the iodometric estimation of the amount of active halogen present in it. It was further characterised by recording its ir spectra and determining its m.p. (130°). Its stock solution (0.05 mol dm⁻³) was prepared in purified acetic acid and standardised.

Phenols studied were phenol, *p*-chloro-, *o*-chloro-, *m*-chloro-, *p*-nitro-, *m*-nitro-, *p*-methyl-, *m*-methyl- and *o*-carboxylic phenols. Pure samples of phenols (Sisco) were redistilled or recrystallised and their stock solutions (0.10 mol dm⁻³) in purified acetic acid were prepared just before use. The stock solutions of benzamide (1.0 mol dm⁻³) in acetic acid, mercuric acetate (0.10 mol dm⁻³) and sodium acetate (1.0 mol dm⁻³) in double-distilled water were used. Acetic acid was purified by refluxing it with chromium(vi) oxide for 5–6 h and distilled (b.p. 118°). Ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.30 mol dm⁻³ using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic studies were made in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [phenol] > [NBB] (5 to 60 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of NBB solution (5.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to the mixtures containing known amounts of phenols (5.0 × 10⁻³ to 6.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (2.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 10 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³), benzamide (0.05–0.30 mol dm⁻³), mercuric acetate (1.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³), sodium perchlorate (or sodium acetate), acetic acid and water, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by iodometric determination of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ± 3%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of NBB-phenol reaction was determined by equilibrating reaction mixtures containing slight excess of NBB over [phenol] in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v). Estimation of unreacted oxidant in the

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED CONSTANTS AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES FOR BROMINATION OF PHENOL AND SUBSTITUTED-PHENOLS BY *N*-BROMOBENZAMIDE IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) AS [SUBSTRATE]₀ AND [BENZAMIDE]₀ ARE VARIED

10 ³ [Phenol] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)								10 ⁴ k recalcd. (s ⁻¹)						Calculated from plots of 1/(k _{obs} - k ₁) [S] vs [BA]	
	in absence of NaOAc		in presence of NaOAc		Calculated from plots of 1/k _{obs} vs [BA]				in absence of NaOAc		in presence of NaOAc					
			<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -COOH	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -COOH	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃		
0.5	—	—	5.7	9.2	8.7	7.6	14.8	11.1	—	12.3	5.1	10.3	8.7	7.8	16.1	12.1
1.0	11.6	13.7	7.7	11.7	10.1	8.8	17.4	13.2	11.9	13.8	7.7	11.9	10.5	8.9	17.6	13.4
2.0	15.3	14.8	8.7	—	11.4	10.2	19.6	14.8	12.8	14.8	10.3	—	11.8	9.7	20.6	15.8
3.0	17.3	15.2	—	15.8	—	—	—	17.7	13.1	15.1	—	13.4	—	—	—	—
4.0	—	15.5	10.4	—	12.1	11.5	24.5	17.7	—	15.3	12.4	—	12.5	10.5	26.6	20.7
5.0	21.3	15.8	—	16.7	12.5	—	26.3	19.5	13.7	15.8	—	16.7	12.7	—	29.6	23.1
10[BA] (mol dm ⁻³)	Calculated from the plots of 1/k _{obs} vs 1/[S]															
0.5	12.8	14.8	10.0	12.3	11.0	9.9	—	—	15.7	15.0	9.3	14.3	11.6	10.0	—	—
1.0	11.6	13.7	7.7	11.7	10.1	8.8	—	—	11.9	13.6	7.7	11.9	10.4	8.9	—	—
2.0	10.4	12.3	5.0	10.6	9.7	7.7	—	—	8.0	11.4	5.6	9.0	8.6	7.0	—	—
3.0	9.3	11.1	3.8	9.6	7.6	6.5	—	—	6.1	9.9	4.5	7.1	7.4	5.7	—	—

reaction mixtures showed that one mole of phenol reacts with one mole of NBB,

Each reactant solution (phenol and *N*-bromobenzamide) was mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio at room temperature. The reaction mixture gradually turned reddish yellow in colour. After completion of reaction, the product was extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was neutralised by NaOH. The reduced product benzamide was precipitated and its m.p. determined (125°, lit. 127°). Evaporation of the ether extract gave a reddish brown semi-solid. An examination of the residue showed that it contains *p*- and *o* bromophenols

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